

Formulation and Evaluation of Oral Floating Dexlansoprazole in situ Gel for Gastroesophageal reflux disease by pH triggered method

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ABSTRACT

In the present study an attempt was made to formulation and evaluation of oral floating Dexlansoprazole in situ gel for Gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD). GERD is a chronic symptom of mucosal damage caused by stomach acid coming up from the stomach into the oesophagus. The preformulation studies for the drugs included API characterization, solubility, melting point, determination of λ_{max} , standard calibrate curve, drug and excipient compatibility study was carried out. Oral floating in situ gel of Dexlansoprazole was formulated by pH triggered method. In pH triggered method, various formulations (F1-F6) were developed using excipients in various concentration of Sodium alginate and HPMC K100M. Formulations were evaluated for various physicochemical parameters like appearance, clarity, pH, gel strength, viscosity, in-vitro gelling capacity, gelling time, in-vitro floating behaviour, drug content and in-vitro drug release studies. As the concentration of the polymer increases properties like gel strength, viscosity found to increasing but whereas the percentage of cumulative drug release from the formulation was decreased. F5 was selected as best formulation because of its good gelling capacity and optimum viscosity. Drug content was found to be $97.25 \pm 0.20\%$. It showed $92.88 \pm 0.1\%$ in vitro drug release for 8h. The F5 formulation follows first order kinetic which describes that the rate of drug release is dependent of its concentration and which is best fit for higuchi kinetic model. Stability studies were carried out for F5 formulations as per ICH guidelines for a period of 90 days and the stability was confirmed as there were no significant changes observed in physicochemical parameters.

Keywords: GERD, in situ gel, Sodium alginate, HPMC K100M, ion activated method.

INTRODUCTION

Gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) is a chronic symptom of mucosal damage caused by stomach acid coming up from stomach into the oesophagus. GERD is caused by the changes in barrier between the stomach and the oesophagus, including abnormal relaxation of the lower oesophageal sphincter. The most common symptoms include heart burn and regurgitation as shown in figure 1. Medications such as proton pump inhibitors, H₂ receptor blockers and antacids are used in the treatment of GERD. DSP is a

proton pump inhibitor drug used in the treatment of GERD. However, it is degraded in acidic stomach pH, thus lacking in pharmacological action of the drug. GERD is a common condition with a prevalence of 10–20% in the Western world and an annual incidence of 0.38–0.45%. The range of GERD prevalence estimate is 18.1–27.8% in North America and 8.8–25.9% in Europe. In the United States (US), 20% of the population experience GERD related symptoms weekly and 7% daily. Several studies have demonstrated that patients with GERD have reduced health-related quality of life and work productivity.¹

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Figure 1: Heart burn and GERD occur

Dexlansoprazole is a medication which reduces stomach acid. So, it is used to treat gastroesophageal reflux disease. Dexlansoprazole is a new generation PPI used for the management of symptoms associated with GERD and erosive esophagitis. Dexlansoprazole is used to heal and maintain healing of erosive esophagitis and to treat heartburn associated with GERD.²

In situ is a Latin word meaning 'in its original place' or 'in position'. *In situ* gelling drug delivery system is capable of releasing drug in a sustained manner, maintaining relatively constant plasma profiles. *In situ* gelling systems are liquid at room temperature but undergo gelation when in contact with body fluids or change in pH. In contrast to very strong gels, they can be easily applied in liquid form to the site of drug absorption. At the site of drug absorption, they swell to form a strong gel that is capable of prolonging the residence time of the active substance. Both natural and synthetic polymers can be used for the production of *in situ* gels. *In situ* gel formation occurs due to one or combination of different stimuli like pH change, temperature modulation and ionic cross-linking.^{3,4}

MATERIALS AND METHOD

MATERIALS:

Dexlansoprazole was supplied as a gift sample from Sri Krishna Pharma Ltd, HPMC K100 M by Yarrow Chem Products, Sodium alginate, Calcium carbonate and Methyl paraben by S D Fine Chem Limited, Sodium citrate by Thomas Chemicals Pvt limited, Calcium chloride by Karnataka Fine Chem, Sodium saccharin by Loba Chemie.

PREFORMULATION STUDIES

Preformulation study is one of the important concerns in development of any drug delivery system. It can be defined as the investigation of physical and chemical properties of the drug substance alone and also in combination with excipients. Thus, a preformulation study was carried out to confirm the compatibility between drug, various polymers and other additives for the betterment of the formulation.

- a) **Solubility:**⁵ The drug was dissolved in different solvents to check their solubility until it forms precipitate and was recorded. The solvents used are dimethylformamide, methanol, ethanol, dichloromethane, ethyl acetate, acetonitrile, water.
- b) **Determination of melting point:**⁶ Melting point was determined by taking small amount of drug separately in a capillary tube closed at one end and placed in a Thiele's melting point apparatus and the temperature at which drug melts was recorded. This was performed in triplicates and average value was reported.
- c) **Determination of λ_{max} of Dexlansoprazole:**⁷ 100mg (0.1gm) of Dexlansoprazole was weighed & transfer to 100ml volumetric flask then dissolved in 0.1N Hcl & volume was made up to the mark with 0.1N Hcl. (1000 μ g/ml). From the above stock 1 solution pipette out 10ml solution & transfer to 100ml volumetric flask & make up to the volume with 0.1N Hcl (100 μ g/ml). From the stock solution 2, obtain a concentration of 10 μ g/ml & scanned over the wavelength range of 400nm to 200nm using UV spectrophotometer

against same solvent as blank. The spectrum of absorbance versus wavelength was recorded & analysed for the absorbance maximum (λ_{max}) & its wavelength.

d) Standard calibrative curve of Dexlansoprazole in 0.1N Hcl: ⁷

Preparation of 0.1N Hcl: 8.5ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid was diluted to 1000ml with distilled water.

100mg (0.1gm) of Dexlansoprazole was weighed & transfer to 100ml volumetric flask then dissolved in 0.1N Hcl & volume was made up to the mark with 0.1N Hcl. From the above stock 1 solution pipette out 10ml solution & transfer to 100ml volumetric flask & make up to the volume with 0.1N Hcl. From the above Stock solution 2 pipette out 1, 1.4, 1.8, 2.2, 2.6ml solution & diluted in 10ml volumetric flask with 0.1N Hcl. Which gives 10, 14, 18, 22, 26, 30 μ g/ml concentration. Absorbance of diluted solution was measured in a UV-visible spectrophotometer at **253nm** wavelength.

e) Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy: ⁸

This study is carried out to find out the compatibility in between the drug and the various excipients, which will be used in the formulation of a dosage form. The sample disc was prepared by triturating approximately 1 or 2 mg of the sample substance with around 10 - 20 mg of KBr

/ Potassium bromide and it is triturated and the triturate is compressed by a hydraulic press in order to form a thin disc of around 10-15mm diameter, which will be sufficient to give an IR spectrum of a suitable intensity. This disc is then placed in a sample holder and it is scanned in the range of 4000-400 cm^{-1} in a FTIR spectrophotometer in order to get a spectrum. The obtained spectra of drug and the excipients are compared and it was interpreted for the functional group peaks in order to check for any major interactions.

METHOD:

Preparation of *in situ* gel by pH triggered method: ^{9,10}

Sodium alginate and sodium citrate were dissolved in a measured quantity of deionized water under continuous stirring. To this solution, HPMC K100M was gradually added and the mixture was stirred for 30 minutes to obtain a uniform polymeric solution. Calcium carbonate was dissolved separately in deionized water and then slowly added to the polymeric solution with continuous stirring. Dexlansoprazole was subsequently added to the resulting mixture and stirred until complete dissolution of the drug was achieved. Finally, the sweetening agent was incorporated, and the volume was adjusted to 100 mL using deionized water to obtain the oral floating *in situ* gel.

Table 1: Formula chart for pH triggered *in situ* gel method

CODE (gm)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
Dexlansoprazole	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30
Sodium alginate	1	1	1	1.25	1.25	1.25
HPMC K100 M	0.25	0.5	0.75	0.25	0.5	0.75
Sodium Citrate	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17
Calcium Chloride	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Sodium Saccharine	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005
Methyl Paraben	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02
Deionized Water (100ml)	100	100	100	100	100	100

Evaluation of prepared *in situ* solution

a) Physical appearance & clarity

All the prepared batches were checked for their appearance, clarity (visually).

b) pH measurement: ¹¹

The pH of the prepared solution for all formulations was measured by digital pH meter at $25 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ after it is calibration using standard buffer solutions of pH 4, 7, 9.2. Then the measurements of pH were recorded as an average of three measurements.

c) Viscosity study:¹²

The viscosity was measured using Brookfield DVT viscometer using LV-3 spindle. The formulation was taken into sample holder and angular velocity increased gradually from 0.3, 0.6, 1.5, 3, 6, 12, 30 and 60 rpm with period of 30 sec at each speed. The viscosity measurement was performed at room temperature. For all the formulation volume of sample was adjusted with the mark given in the spindle to measure accurate viscosity. The interpretation of results or viscometer dial reading are converted to a viscosity value in units of centipoise, multiply the reading noted on dial viscometer by the appropriate factor.

d) Floating behaviour:¹³

The time taken by the gel to reach the top from the bottom position of the dissolution flask is termed as Floating lag time. The floating lag time of the gel was determination by performing an visual inspection in a USP dissolution test apparatus, which contains 900 ml of 0.1 N HCl (pH of 1.2) at temperature $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$.

e) Gelling time:¹⁴

Gelling time was determined by mixing each of the 5ml formulation with 0.1 N HCl (approx. 50 ml) pH 1.2 in a beaker and the gelation was assessed by visual examination. The time required for the detection of gelation of in situ gelling system is noted down as gelling time and the integrity of gel was also observed.

f) Gel strength:¹⁵

50 ml of the formulation was placed in a 100 ml graduated cylinder and gelled by adding pH 1.2 buffer. Weight of 50 gm was placed onto the gel surface for measuring gel strength. Then gel strength, which is an indication of the ability of formed gel to maintain its integrity was measured as time in seconds. The time taken by the weight to penetrate 5

cm down through the gel was noted down as gel strength.

g) In vitro gelation study:¹³

The *in-vitro* gelling capacity of prepared formulations was measured by using visual method. 5 ml of the gelation solution i.e. 0.1N HCl of pH 1.2 was placed in a 15 ml borosilicate glass test tube and it was maintained at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ temperature. One ml of the formulation solution was added to gelation solution by using pipette. As the solution comes in contact with the gelation solution, it is expected to get converted into stiff gel like structure immediately. The gelling capacity of the resulting solution is evaluated on the basis of stiffness of the gel formed. The gelling capacity of solution was graded in three categories evaluated on the basis of stiffness of formed gel and time period for which the gel retained its rigidity.

(+) Gels after few minutes dispersed rapidly.

(++) Gelation immediate remains for few hours.

(+++) Gelation immediate remains for an extended period.

h) Drug content uniformity:¹⁶

Prepared 10 ml of *in situ* gel (containing equivalent to 30 mg of Dexlansoprazole) from different batches was transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask. To this 70 ml 0.1 N HCl was added and sonicated for 30 minutes. After that volume was adjusted to 100 ml with 0.1 N HCl. From this solution 1 ml of sample was withdrawn and diluted to 10 ml with 0.1 N HCl. The absorbance of these solutions was measured in UV-Visible spectrophotometer at 253nm against same dilutions without drug as a blank solution.

i) In vitro dissolution studies:¹⁷

The drug release study was carried out using USP type-II apparatus (Rotating Paddle type) at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ and 50 rpm using 900 ml of 0.1 N HCl as a dissolution medium. 10ml (equivalent to 30mg of Dexlansoprazole) was used for the study. 5 ml of sample solution was withdrawn at predetermined time intervals in 10ml volumetric flask and volume was makeup with 0.1N HCl. Equal amount of fresh

dissolution medium was replaced immediately after withdrawal of the test sample. After performing suitable dilution samples were analysed spectrophotometrically at 253 nm.

j) Drug release kinetic studies:¹⁸⁻²⁰

The drug release kinetic studies were done by various mathematical models (zero order, first order, Higuchi's square root, Hixson-Crowell cube root law and Korsmeyer Peppas model). The model that best fits the release data is selected based on the regression coefficient (R^2) value in various models. The model that gives high ' R^2 ' value is considered as the best fit of the release data.

k) Stability studies:²¹

The purpose of stability study is to provide evidence that the quality of a drug substance or drug product will not vary with time under the influence of a variety of environmental factors such as temperature, humidity and light during the storage period before consumption of the product. Stability studies were performed for the formulation which was selected as best as per ICH guidelines. The formulation was sealed in an aluminium foil and stored at specified condition $40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $75 \pm 5\%$ RH for 90 days. Samples were periodically taken and evaluated for physicochemical parameter, drug content and in vitro

release using the same procedure mentioned previously.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preformulation studies

- Drug description:** This study is important as organoleptic property determination is a preliminary test for each and every drug. The nature, colour & odour of Dexlansoprazole are complying with their specifications that is mentioned as in various literature sources.
- Solubility:** Solubility studies were carried out in different solvents as per I.P. Dexlansoprazole was found to be freely soluble in methanol, ethanol and dimethylformamide. Very soluble in 0.1N Hcl, slightly soluble in water, soluble in acetonitrile.
- Melting point determination:** Melting point of Dexlansoprazole was found to be 139°C , it is within the near standard range of 140°C , which showed that the procured drug is free from impurities.
- Determination of λ_{max} of Dexlansoprazole:** Determination of λ_{max} of Dexlansoprazole in 0.1N Hcl was carried and found to be 238.50nm .

Figure 2: Determination of λ_{max} of Dexlansoprazole

- Standard calibrative curve of Dexlansoprazole:** The standard calibrative curve of Dexlansoprazole in 0.1N Hcl was carried out at 253nm. The regression equation was $y = 0.0351x + 0.0008$ and regression coefficient was found to

be $R^2 = 0.9992$ as shown in Figure 3. By using the value of regression coefficient %CDR was calculated. The standard calibration curve obeys Beer's law as concentration increases absorbance also increases.

Figure 3: Standard Calibrative Curve of Dexlansoprazole in 0.1N HCl

f) **FT IR Spectroscopy Compatibility Studies:**

Drug and polymer compatibility studies were carried out by *FT IR* technique to study any interaction of polymer with the drug in the formulation. The pure Dexlansoprazole showed principal absorption peaks at 3523.19 (NH Stretching), 1043.87 (S=O Stretching), 637.27 (C-S Stretching), 1176.27 (C-F Stretching),

1274.41 (C-N Stretching), 2992.61 (CH Stretching Hetero Aromatic), 1408.24 (C-C Stretching Phenyl) and 705.38 (C-C Bending). The *FT IR* study showed that there is no interaction between drug and polymer because it shows the characteristic peak of drug and polymers. Therefore, the drug and polymers used are compatible with each other as shown in Figure 4-7

Figure 4. *FT-IR* Spectra of Dexlansoprazole

Figure 5. FT-IR Spectra of Drug and Sodium alginate**Figure7. FT-IR Spectra of Drug, HPMC K100M and Sodium Alginate****EVALUATION TEST**

- a) Physical appearance & clarity:** The *in-situ* gels formulations (F1-F6) are evaluated for their appearance & clarity. All formulations (F1-F6) were opaque in their appearance and their clarity is clear.
- b) pH measurement:** Formulation F1 to F6 were checked for their pH using calibrated pH meter. The pH of the formulations was found to be in the range of 7.14–7.87. The measurement of pH of each formulation were in triplicate and the average values along with standard deviation.

- c) Viscosity:** The rheological properties of the solutions are importance in viewing of their proposed oral administration. The formulation should have an optimum viscosity that will allow easy swallowing as a liquid, which then undergoes a rapid sol–gel transition due to ionic interaction. The order of viscosity of all formulations were $F6 > F5 > F4 > F3 > F2 > F1$ as shown in Figure 8. The formulations showed a marked increase in viscosity with increasing concentration of Sodium alginate and HPMC K100M. The formulations obey non Newtonian flow (pseudo plastic flow).

Figure 8: Viscosity of ion activated formulation F1-F6

d) Floating behaviour:

i. Floating lag time: The floating lag time of all the prepared formulations (F1 to F6) was determined by using 0.1N HCl (pH 1.2). The floating lag time was found to be in between 11 to 27 sec as shown in table 2. The higher polymer concentrations will help in shortening of time taken by the formulation to float completely over the surface of the dissolution medium. This may be due to the higher cross-linking density at

higher polymer concentrations, which could effectively trap the CO₂ bubbles so that density of the gel is reduced rapidly to induce buoyancy.

ii. Floating duration: The floating duration of all the prepared formulations (F1 to F6) was determined by using 0.1N HCl (pH 1.2) and it was found out that all the formulations were able to float for more than the period of 8 hours except F1 formulation (7hrs) as shown in table 2.

Table 2: Floating Lag time & Floating Duration of *in situ* gelling formulation (F1-F6)

Formulation code	Floating lag time (sec)	Floating duration (hrs)
F1	27	7
F2	24	8
F3	20	8
F4	18	12
F5	14	12
F6	11	>12

e) Gelling time: Gelling time of the formulations was assessed by visual examination. Gelling time found to be varied according to the concentration of the polymer used proportionally. The gelling time of formulations F1-F6 was found to be 10-21 seconds as shown in table 3.

remains for an extended period of time but they form stiff gel due to the higher concentration of Sodium alginate and HPMC K100M as shown in table 3.

f) *In-vitro* gelling capacity: Formulation F1 formed gelation within few minutes but it was dispersed rapidly due to less concentration of Sodium alginate. Formulations F2 to F4 shows formed gelation immediately and remains for few hours which shows good property of gelation. In case of formulations F5 to F6 formed immediate gel and

g) Gel Strength: Gel strength of all the formulations was determined. Formulation F3 to F6 shows good gel strength. F1- F2 shows poor gel strength. Gel strength found to depend on the concentration of the polymers used in the formulation. As the concentration increased the gel strength was also found to be increased proportionally as shown in table

Table 3: Gelling time, *In-vitro* Gelling Capacity & Gel Strength

Formulation Code	Gelling time (sec)	<i>In-vitro</i> Gelling Capacity	Gel Strength
F1	21	+	Poor
F2	18	++	Poor
F3	17	++	Good
F4	15	++	Good
F5	11	+++	Good
F6	10	+++	Good

h) Drug content: The drug content of the formulations (F1 to F6) was found to be in the range of $94.27 \pm 0.07\%$ to $97.25 \pm 0.20\%$ as

shown in table 4. which were within the limit (not < 94% and not > 106%) as specified in U.S.P. This study concludes that the drug is uniformly distributed in the formulation.

Table 4: Drug content of formulation F1-F6

Formulation Code	% Drug Content
F1	96.66 ± 0.21
F2	94.95 ± 0.18
F3	94.27 ± 0.07
F4	95.57 ± 0.05
F5	97.25 ± 0.20
F6	94.49 ± 0.19

i) *In vitro* dissolution studies: The *in vitro* drug release study of Dexlansoprazole from all the formulations were conducted for a period of 8 hours in 0.1N Hcl (pH 1.2). The highest drug release was observed $96.98 \pm 0.04\%$ in F1 formulation and lowest drug release was $76.09 \pm$

0.31% in F9 formulation. From the comparative *in vitro* drug release for formulations (F1-F6) was characterized by an initial phase of high release followed by second phase of moderate release due to increase in concentration of polymers. The comparative *in vitro* dissolution profiles as shown in Table 5.

Table 5: %CDR of formulation (F1-F6)

Time (hrs)	% CDR (F1-F6)					
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
1	36.23 ± 0.29	35.44 ± 0.2	31.02 ± 0.4	27.70 ± 0.15	23.04 ± 0.19	21.26 ± 0.11
2	46.47 ± 0.6	43.12 ± 0.16	39.89 ± 0.15	35.03 ± 0.8	32.66 ± 0.6	33.58 ± 0.3
3	51.73 ± 0.7	51.08 ± 0.14	43.81 ± 0.6	44.21 ± 0.5	44.92 ± 0.14	41.49 ± 0.3
4	63.06 ± 0.2	56.85 ± 0.02	50.91 ± 0.5	53.06 ± 0.19	55.72 ± 0.2	50.55 ± 0.2
5	72.71 ± 0.9	60.92 ± 0.1	56.48 ± 0.2	62.26 ± 0.6	65.48 ± 0.17	57.49 ± 0.18
6	80.50 ± 0.5	67.80 ± 0.08	68.19 ± 0.16	68.84 ± 0.24	74.80 ± 0.9	64.47 ± 0.33
7	87.88 ± 0.8	70.86 ± 0.31	73.84 ± 0.09	82.00 ± 0.08	83.47 ± 0.09	74.37 ± 0.34
8	93.43 ± 0.12	80.32 ± 0.05	79.03 ± 0.37	88.25 ± 0.6	92.88 ± 0.1	85.65 ± 0.4

j) Drug release kinetic studies: All the prepared formulation was fitted in zero order release, first order release, Higuchi model and Korsmeyer

peppas model based on the *in vitro* drug release data. The dissolution data of all formulations was found to be best fitted in first order showing that

the drug release is dependent on concentration of polymers and follows Higuchi mechanism as shown in Figure 10-13.

10. Zero order Kinetic release (F1-F6)

11. First order Kinetic release (F1-F6)

12. Higuchi plot of formulation F1-F6

13. Korsmeyer Peppas Plot of formulation F1- F6

Table 6: In vitro drug release kinetics studies

Formulation	Zero-order	First-order	Higuchi	Korsmeyer–Peppas		Best Fit Model	Release Mechanism
	R ²	R ²	R ²	R ²	n		
F1	0.975	0.981	0.991	0.988	0.62	Higuchi	Non-Fickian
F2	0.964	0.973	0.986	0.981	0.58	Higuchi	Non-Fickian
F3	0.969	0.977	0.989	0.984	0.60	Higuchi	Non-Fickian
F4	0.972	0.979	0.992	0.987	0.66	Higuchi	Non-Fickian
F5	0.978	0.983	0.994	0.989	0.69	Higuchi	Non-Fickian
F6	0.967	0.974	0.988	0.982	0.57	Higuchi	Non-Fickian

In-vitro dissolution studies were carried out for 8 hours. The regression coefficient of (F1-F6) formulation follows Higuchi type of drug release. Korsmeyer–Peppas analysis showed n values between 0.57 and 0.69 which indicates that those formulations show drug release by non-Fickian release.

k) Stability studies: Stability studies was carried out on the selected best formulations F5 as per ICH Guidelines. The formulation was stored in sealed aluminium foil at $45 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, $75 \pm 5\%$ RH for 90 days. Formulation was periodically evaluated for physicochemical parameter such as pH, viscosity, floating lag time, gelling capacity,

gelling time, drug content, *in vitro* drug release & no significant changes were observed while comparing with the initial results which ensures the stability of the formulation.

Selection of best formulation: The selection of the best batch depends on viscosity, drug content, % cumulative drug release from the formulation. Formulation F5 may be selected as the best batches. They have good gelling capacity and optimum viscosity compared to other formulations. F5 shows drug content $97.25 \pm 0.20\%$ respectively, which were within the limit (not $< 94\%$ and not $> 106\%$) as specified in U.S.P. The viscosity of batch F5 was found to be 12000-240 cps which is favourable for swallowing and has good ability for gelation. Cumulative drug release of F5 was $92.88 \pm 0.1\%$ after 8 hours, which may give complete release in 10 hrs. So, the F5 was selected as the best formulation.

CONCLUSION

Oral floating *in situ* gel of Dexlansoprazole was formulated by ion activated method. In ion activated method, various formulations (F1-F6) were developed using excipients in various concentrations of Sodium alginate and HPMC K100M. Formulations were evaluated for various physicochemical parameters. By analysing the results, the various properties of the prepared gelling system were found to be proportional to the concentration of polymer. As the concentration of the polymer increases, properties like gel strength, viscosity were found to increase but whereas the percentage of cumulative drug release from the formulation was decreased. F5 was selected as the best formulation because of its good gelling capacity and optimum viscosity. Drug content was found to be $97.25 \pm 0.20\%$. It showed $92.88 \pm 0.1\%$ cumulative drug release for 8h. The formulation F5 best fitted for first order kinetics for drug release which describes that the rate of drug release is dependent of its concentration and follows Higuchi kinetic mechanism. Stability studies were carried out for F5 formulations as per ICH guidelines for a period of 90 days and the stability was confirmed as there were no significant changes observed in physicochemical parameters. Hence the prepared *in situ* gel of Dexlansoprazole was found to be prepared successfully. The oral *in situ* gel

improves patient compliance by reducing the frequency of the dosing

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